

The Efficacy of Cognitive Restructuring in Treating Insomnia and Fatigue among University Students with Somatic Symptoms Complaints

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ABSTRACT: The primary objective of the current research was to explore the efficacy of Cognitive Restructuring (CR) in treating insomnia and fatigue among university students with somatic symptom complaints. It was hypothesized that there would be a notable distinction in the score of insomnia, fatigue, and somatic symptoms between the pre-test and post-test scores after receiving Cognitive Restructuring. The sample of the study (n=313) was collected through Simple Random Sampling from a public sector university of Peshawar, KPK. The age range of the participants was between 18-30 years (M=1.52, SD=5.31). Among 313 participants, n=21 received Cognitive Restructuring. A 6-week therapeutic program was implemented. The Somatic Symptom Scale-8, Regensburg's Insomnia Scale, and Fatigue Assessment Scale were used for somatic symptom complaints, insomnia, and fatigue, respectively. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test, and Simple Linear Regression were used for statistical analyses. The results showed that Cognitive Restructuring promisingly reduced insomnia, fatigue, and somatic symptoms. While on Simple Linear Regression, somatic symptoms were the strongest predictor of fatigue and insomnia ($p<.001$).

Keywords: somatic symptoms, insomnia, fatigue, cognitive restructuring, university students

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1. Introduction

Somatic Symptoms

Around 20% of individuals seeking primary health care across the globe report physical symptoms that cannot be attributed to any general medical ailment, even after a thorough assessment and testing process. Such symptoms, often known as “medically unexplained symptoms (MUS)” in addition to some explainable symptoms, have come to be generally known as somatic symptoms (Scamvougeras & Howard, 2020). Somatic symptoms are symptoms that do or do not have clearly demonstrable pathophysiologic correlates. Although most somatic symptoms are temporary or do not lead to dysfunction, in some cases, however, they might progress into being more disabling or even into full meet

criteria of somatoform abnormalities, which are linked to significant disability and hospitalizations. Additionally, somatic symptoms may even negatively affect the course or development of other psychiatric disorders (Mewes, 2022).

Insomnia and Somatic Symptoms

Sleep concerns may also be a hallmark of the somatic presentation. While the literature is limited in examining the interaction of sleep and somatic complaints broadly, patients with chronic pain (who often report high somatic symptoms) report higher levels of sleep difficulties. This includes greater reports of insomnia symptoms, poorer sleep hygiene, higher pre-sleep arousal, and more bedtime resistance, all of which can impact functioning. While it is determined that these sleep complaints are likely to occur in pain populations, it is not yet known how common or problematic somatic symptoms are in youth with primary sleep complaints (Valrie et al., 2013).

Nordin et al. (2021) examined a relationship specifically between insomnia, and somatic symptoms. The individual with somatic symptom most commonly reported physical pain such as back aches, stomach pains, nausea, dizziness, and irritable bowel syndrome and have association with sleep disturbance in greater extent. Likewise, the risk of sleep disturbance increased by 1.44 times for each additional somatic symptom.

Fatigue and Somatic Symptoms

Numerous studies have examined the relationship between fatigue and somatic symptoms, with many studies emphasizing the overlap of biological, cognitive, and behavioural variables. According to Liu et al. (2019) found dysfunction of serotonin and noradrenaline play crucial function in the occurrence of somatic symptoms and fatigue by impairing brain signalling. These anomalies in the neurotransmitter system may result in persistent feelings of physical symptoms and fatigue, which would feed the loop of somatic symptoms and fatigue. Patients who experience somatic problems in addition to chronic fatigue, especially those who are under a lot of stress or emotional pressure, exhibit this physiological overlap.

Another study by Abbass et al. (2021) emphasizes how prolonged fatigue aggravates somatic symptoms, including gastrointestinal issues and muscle tightness. Given the combined effects of physical and mental strain, their findings imply that people with both illnesses have more difficulty managing everyday activities and preserving quality of life. This combination has the potential to exacerbate functional impairment, especially in situations when stress levels are high or support networks are insufficient.

Furthermore, Henningsen et al. (2023) emphasize how behavioral reactions, including prolonged rest or inactivity brought on by fatigue, can cause physical deconditioning and exacerbate somatic symptoms. This dynamic interplay implies that treating somatic symptoms and fatigue at the same time may be crucial to ending this cycle. Their results suggest all-encompassing strategies that address psychological resilience as well as physical conditioning.

Fatigue and Insomnia

Fatigue and sleep disorders, especially insomnia, are proven to be significantly correlated with each increasing the other. Gates et al. (2018b) suggest that fatigue and insufficient sleep are positively correlated and have a strong association. The symptoms associated with fatigue, including lack of concentration and attention, lack of will to work, and irritable mood, were all significantly associated with the lack of adequate sleep due to insomnia. Additionally, both fatigue and insomnia together were proven to be strong predictors of other mental health-related issues and disorders.

Few studies have been conducted to study the subjective perception of fatigue in insomnia, as well as the association between fatigue and sleeplessness. According to some studies exhaustion is thought to be solely brought on by sleep deprivation which may be the gap of this literature (Fortier-Brochu et al., 2010), therefore some studies suggested that people with high sleep deprivation may have high exhaustion level as compared to those individuals who do not report insomnia. (Harris et al., 2020).

Cognitive Restructuring

Cognitive restructuring (CR) is defined as structured, goal-directed, and collaborative intervention strategies that focus on the exploration, evaluation, and substitution of the maladaptive thoughts, appraisals, and beliefs that maintain psychological disturbance. As far goal is related to systematic cognitive change which included: change in cognition and change in behaviour therefore intervention fall under the definition of cognitive restructuring (Clark, 2013).

Cognitive restructuring (CR) is a core component of the widely known Cognitive-Behavioural Therapy (CBT) and was created by Aaron T. Beck. CR is among the most commonly employed, significantly effective, and more directive techniques from the much broader realm of the whole CBT (Ezawa & Hollon, 2023).

Cognitive Restructuring for Somatic Symptoms

Cognitive restructuring (CR) plays a significant role in helping individuals manage somatic symptoms by addressing maladaptive thoughts that exacerbate bodily discomfort. CR is effective in reducing distress associated with these symptoms by reframing negative or catastrophic interpretations of physical sensations, which are common in individuals who experience persistent bodily symptoms not fully explained by medical conditions. For example, CR challenges automatic thoughts like "I must be seriously ill because I feel unwell," replacing them with more balanced perspectives such as, "This sensation is unpleasant but not necessarily a sign of severe illness."

A study by Orzechowska et al. (2021) in Psychosomatic Medicine showed that CR is effective in reducing symptom severity by helping individuals reinterpret their bodily sensations in a less threatening way. This research suggests that patients who engaged in CR had significant reductions in distress and improved quality of life by learning to interpret physical sensations as manageable rather than catastrophic. The study highlights CR's role

in targeting hypervigilance and worry about bodily sensations, ultimately helping individuals experience relief from somatic distress (Orzechowska et al., 2021).

Cognitive Restructuring for Insomnia

In the context of insomnia, cognitive restructuring is a core element of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Insomnia (CBT-I). Individuals with insomnia often experience cognitive distortions, such as catastrophizing thoughts about their ability to sleep or its impact on functioning. These thought patterns, like “If I don’t sleep perfectly, I won’t function tomorrow,” lead to heightened anxiety around sleep and perpetuate the insomnia cycle.

Research by Kaplin and Harvey (2021) discusses how cognitive restructuring helps patients challenge unrealistic beliefs about sleep and substitute them with balanced thoughts, thus reducing sleep-related anxiety. For example, shifting the thought “I need eight hours of sleep to be functional” to “Even with a few hours of sleep, I can still manage my day” has been shown to reduce the stress that can keep individuals awake. The restructuring process helps break the cycle of pre-sleep worry, leading to better sleep quality (Kaplin and Harvey, 2021).

Cognitive Restructuring for Fatigue

Chronic fatigue can be worsened by negative beliefs about one's ability to manage energy and perform daily tasks. Individuals with chronic fatigue often harbor beliefs like “I can’t do anything because of my fatigue,” which may lead to a cycle of inactivity and further fatigue. Cognitive restructuring targets these beliefs, helping individuals to adopt a more balanced perspective on their abilities and fatigue levels.

A study by Adamson et al. (2020) highlights that cognitive restructuring in chronic fatigue patients focuses on reinterpreting thoughts like “I must conserve all energy” to “I can gradually engage in activities without worsening my fatigue.” This reframing process has shown effectiveness in improving motivation and reducing fatigue severity, as patients begin to engage in low-intensity activities that build endurance over time without exacerbating symptoms (Adamson et al., 2020).

Objectives

1. To find the prevalence of somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue among University students
2. To assess the efficacy of Cognitive Restructuring (CR) on somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue
3. To analyze the effect of somatic symptoms on insomnia and fatigue

Hypotheses

H1: There will be a significantly high prevalence of somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue among University students.

H2: There will be a significant difference in the scores of somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue before and after the administration of Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR)

H3: The somatic symptoms will be a significant predictor of insomnia and fatigue.

2. Method

Research Design

The current research has employed randomized control trials to evaluate the efficacy of Cognitive Restructuring (CR) in treating insomnia and fatigue among university students with Somatic Symptom Complaints. Data were collected at two levels: pre-intervention and post-intervention to assess treatment outcomes.

Sample Size

The total population of university students was 1600. At a 95% confidence interval, the sample was calculated to be 310 using Raosoft. The sample of the study (n=313) was collected through a simple random sampling technique from a public sector university of Peshawar, KPK. The average age range of the university students was 18-30 years (M=1.52, SD=.531). Among 311 university students, 42 students were screened through the Somatic Symptom Scale-8, Regensburg's Insomnia Scale, and Fatigue Assessment Scale. Furthermore, n=21 was allocated to the Cognitive Restructuring group, out of which n=17 completed the treatment with (n=7) males and (n=10) females.

Inclusion Criteria

- The participants who scored 13 or higher on the Somatic Symptom Scale-8 were included in the study.
- The participants in the study were those who had score of 13 or higher on the Regensburg Insomnia Scale.
- The who scored 23 or higher on the Fatigue Assessment Scale were included in the study.
- The participants who were currently enrolled students in the BS Programme at the university were included in the study.
- The participants who showed a willingness to attend all sessions of the therapy and complete the assessment were part of the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- The participants who were/ have been diagnosed with a psychiatric disorder were excluded from the study.
- The participants who were currently on psychotropic medications for somatic symptoms, insomnia, and/or fatigue (that could confound the study variables) were excluded from the study.
- The participants who were receiving another structured psychological intervention for somatic symptoms, insomnia, and/or fatigue were excluded from the study.
- The participants who showed an unwillingness to attend all sessions of the therapy and complete the assessment were excluded from the study.

Instruments

Demographic questionnaire

The demographic sheet was used for evaluating sociodemographic characteristics like age, gender, class/semester, departments, marital status, socioeconomic status, family system, contact information, and a question about willingness to participate in the study.

Somatic Symptom Scale - 8 (SSS-8)

The Somatic Symptom Scale-8 (SSS-8; Gierk et al., 2014). It was first constructed to measure criterion A of the new definition of SSD in DSM-5. It consists of 8 items that assess symptoms along the gastrointestinal, pain, cardiopulmonary, and exhaustion. The SSS-8 specifically assesses the severity of stomach or bowel problems, backaches, pain in limbs, headache, chest pain, dizziness, fatigue, and insomnia. The scoring is done on a 5-point Likert scale such as 0=Not at all, 4=Very much (Gierk et al., 2014). A score of 13 or higher indicated clinically significant levels of somatic symptoms. The internal consistency of the scale is .81.

Regensburg's Insomnia Scale (RIS)

The Regensburg Insomnia Scale was developed by Cronlein et al. in 2013. The RIS is a 10-item self-report measure used to assess the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects of psychophysiological insomnia. The scoring of the scale is completed on a 5-point Likert scale such as 4-Always, 3- Mostly, 2- Sometimes, 1- Seldom, and 0- Never. Item 9th is reverse scored. A score of 0-12 is considered normal, and hence, a score of 13 or higher indicates significant levels of insomnia (Crönlein et al., 2013). The Cronbach's alpha reliability of the scale is .66.

Fatigue Assessment Scale (FAS)

The Fatigue Assessment Scale (FAS) was developed by Michielsen et al. (2003). The FAS is a 10-item self-report measure used to assess the severity of fatigue. Fatigue is assessed as a unidimensional construct and is not divided into factors in FAS. However, to ensure that it measures all aspects of fatigue, the FAS measures both the physical and cognitive aspects of fatigue (Michielsen et al., 2003). The scoring of the scale consists of a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (i.e., 1- Never, 2- Sometimes, 3- Regularly, 4- Often, and 5- Always)-Always. Items 4th and 10th are reverse-scored. The Cronbach's alpha reliability of the scale is .80.

Procedure

The study formally began by taking information regarding the number of total departments and currently enrolled students in the BS program of each department from the Director of Admissions of the university. The Director of Admissions provided information regarding 22 departments in total. Out of these 22 departments, 6 were selected through a lottery method. The total number of students in the BS program of these 6 departments was 1600.

In the next step, formal permission letters were signed by the chairpersons of each of these departments so as to seek permission to collect data from their respective departments. Afterwards, through the Systematic Random Sampling technique, the nth (2nd) number of students from the attendance list of each class/semester of the selected departments were chosen for the screening process. As per the sample size calculated by Raosoft, 313 students were selected for the screening process. Then they were provided with the demographic sheet, Somatic Symptom Scale-8, Regensburg's Insomnia Scale, and Fatigue Assessment Scale to assess the occurrence and severity of the study variables.

Once the screening process was completed and the participants who did not meet the inclusion criteria (n=257) as well as those who did not want to participate (n=14), were excluded, the remaining participants were asked to read carefully and then sign a consent form detailing all the necessary information regarding the present study including its objectives, procedures, potential risks and benefits, use of data, confidentiality, voluntary participation, and consent to participate.

Subsequently, through the Block Randomization technique, the participants were allocated (n=21) in the Cognitive Restructuring group. Thereupon, the therapy sessions were formally initiated.

Cognitive Restructuring

Cognitive restructuring was conducted as a group therapy technique in the span of 6 weekly sessions. Each session was 45-60 minutes long. There were 3 groups of participants on the basis of scheduled therapeutic sessions, consisting of 5-6 individuals each. The main agenda of each session was as follows:

Session 1: Introduction, Ice Breaking, and Overview of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy

Session 2: Thought Records, Belief Evaluation, and Thought Evaluation

Session 3: Cognitive Restructuring and Identifying Triggers

Session 4: Cognitive Restructuring, Evidence Analysis, and Thought Reframing

Session 5: Cognitive Restructuring and Practical Implementation of Reframed Thoughts

Session 6: Feedback, Participant Evaluation, Debriefing, and Post-intervention Post Assessment

3. Results

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants

	Variable	N	%
Age	18-20	153	48%
	21-25	153	48%
	26-30	5	1.6%
Gender	Male	159	50%

Education	Female	154	49%
	Semester 1	61	19%
	Semester 4	113	36%
	Semester 6	92	29%
	Semester 8	47	15%
Department	Psychology	89	28%
	Chemistry	43	13%
	Political Science	46	14%
	Economics	34	10%
	Botany	41	13%
	Computer Science	60	19%
Marital Status	Single	285	91%
	Married	28	8.6%
Socioeconomic Status	Lower	14	4.5%
	Middle	276	88%
	Upper	22	7%
Family System	Joint	161	52%
	Nuclear	152	48%

Table 1 indicates the major socio-demographic characteristics of the total sample. Frequencies (N) and percentages (%) of each level of characteristic are shown.

Table 2: Alpha Reliability of the Study Variables

Scales	M	SD	Range	Cronbach's Alpha
SSS	9.27	6.84	0-29	.806
RIS	14.20	6.23	1-32	.664
FAS	24.91	6.35	10-45	.663

Note: SSS= Somatic Symptoms Scale-8, RIS= Regensburg's Insomnia Scale, FAS= Fatigue Assessment Scale

Table 2 indicates the psychometric properties of the major study variables, i.e., Somatic Symptoms (SSS), Insomnia (RIS), and Fatigue (FAS). The results indicated that SSS (M=9.27, SD=6.84) showed good reliability with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.8 and consisted of 8 items, whereas RIS (M=14.20, SD=6.23) and FAS (M=24.91, SD=6.35) showed an average reliability with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.66 and consisted of 10 items each.

Table 3: Correlation and Descriptive Statistics of Major Study Variables

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4
Gender	1.49	.501	-			
SSS	9.27	6.84	.382**	-		
RIS	14.20	6.23	-.111*	.343**	-	
FAS	24.91	6.35	.142*	.426**	.322**	-

Note: SSS= Somatic Symptoms Scale-8, RIS= Regensburg's Insomnia Scale, FAS= Fatigue Assessment Scale

Table 3 shows the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation between SSS, RIS, and FAS. The results show that Somatic symptoms (SSS) are positively correlated with Insomnia (RIS) ($r=.343$, $p<0.01$) and Fatigue (FAS) ($r=.426$, $p<0.01$), indicating that higher scores of Somatic symptoms complaints are associated with greater levels of Insomnia and Fatigue. Additionally, there is a positive correlation between Insomnia and Fatigue ($r=.322$, $p<0.01$), indicating that higher levels of Insomnia contribute to a higher level of Fatigue. Possible gender differences in symptom reporting is indicated by a weak correlation between gender and somatic symptom ($r=.322$, $p<0.01$) and fatigue ($r=.142$, $p<0.05$), whereas a negative correlation between gender and insomnia ($r= -.111$, $p<0.05$).

Table 4: Mean Comparison of Pre-intervention and Post-intervention on Somatic Symptoms Scale-8, Regensburg's Insomnia Scale, and Fatigue Assessment Scale of Cognitive Restructuring Group (n=17)

Variable	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention		Z	p	r*
	M	SD	M	SD			
SSS	19.47	4.70	8.35	4.03	3.62	< .001	0.62
RIS	20.0	5.01	11.06	4.32	3.62	< .001	0.62
FAS	31.35	6.90	22.53	4.71	3.17	< .001	0.54

Note: SSS= Somatic Symptom Scale-8, RIS= Regensburg's Insomnia Scale, FAS= Fatigue Assessment Scale, r= effect size of Wilcoxon signed-rank test. $P< .001^{***}$

In table 4, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test was conducted to assess whether there was a statistically significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores following the Cognitive restructuring intervention. The results revealed a significant difference between the pre- and post-scores of somatic symptoms ($z=3.62$, $p<0.001$), insomnia ($z=3.62$, $p<0.001$), and fatigue ($z=3.17$, $p<0.001$). The Ranks table showed that there were no positive ranks ($N=0$), indicating that no post-test scores were greater than the pre-test scores. In contrast, there were 17 negative ranks ($N=17$), demonstrating that all post-test scores were lower than the pre-test scores. The results suggest a significant reduction in the severity of somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue following the CR intervention.

Table 5: Regression Coefficient of Somatic Symptoms Scale-8 on Regensburg's Insomnia Scale

Variable	B	β	SE
Constant	11.29***	-	.599
SSS	.313***	.049	.343
R_2	.118		
ΔR_2	.118		

Note: SSS= Somatic Symptom Scale-8, RIS= Regensburg's Insomnia Scale. $P<.001^{***}$

Simple linear regression was used to assess whether somatic symptoms (SSS) significantly predicted insomnia (RIS) among the participants. The results in Table 5 indicated that SSS predicted 11.8% of the variance in RIS ($R^2=.118$, $F(1,311)=41.51$, $p<.001$). It was found that SSS significantly predicted RIS ($\beta=.049$, $p<.001$).

Table 6: Regression Coefficient of Somatic Symptoms Scale-8 on Fatigue Assessment Scale

Variable	B	β	SE
Constant	21.26***	-	.555
SSS	.391***	.420	.048
R ₂	.176		
ΔR_2	.176		

Note: SSS= Somatic Symptom Scale-8, FAS= Fatigue Assessment Scale P<.001

Simple linear regression was used to assess whether somatic symptoms (SSS) significantly predicted fatigue (FAS) among the participants. The results in Table 6 indicated that SSS predicted 17.6% of the variance in FAS ($R^2=.176$, $F(1,309)=61.11$, $p<.001$). It was found that SSS significantly predicted RIS ($\beta=.420$, $p<.001$).

4. Discussion

The current study aimed to explore the efficacy of Cognitive Restructuring (CR) in treating insomnia and fatigue among university students with somatic symptom complaints.

The primary objective of the present study was to determine the prevalence of somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue among university students. The descriptive findings of the study indicate that a substantial part of the study sample (18.6%) exhibited clinically significant levels of co-occurring somatic symptom complaints, insomnia, and fatigue. These results align with the existing literature, such as (Zahid et al., 2024b); Shahzadi et al. (2023) and Hanif et al. (2024) who reported a medium-high prevalence rate of somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue, respectively, among Pakistani students.

The second objective of the present study, i.e., a crucial difference between the pretest and post-test scores for cognitive restructuring has also been found significant. The results of the current study illustrate that there was a statistically significant difference between the pre- and post-intervention scores across all the variables, i.e., somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue, following the conduction of cognitive restructuring programme. The outcomes of the present study are consistent with existing literature, illustrating that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)-based therapies and techniques can successfully reduce somatic symptom complaints and associated psychological discomfort. A pilot study by Jongsma et al. (2023) concluded that participating in a six-session CBT-based intervention reduced somatic symptom disorder (SSD) symptoms, as well as associated anxiety, sadness, stress, and perceived impairment. Furthermore, the study revealed that such group sessions could lead to lower healthcare consumption among people with SSD, emphasizing the potential long-term benefits of structured psychological interventions for treating somatic symptoms.

Similarly, the findings of the present study, indicating that a CBT-based technique like cognitive restructuring is significantly effective in treating insomnia and sleep-related problems, are also consistent with the existing literature. Prior studies, like that of Tadros et al. (2024), have reported reduced sleep onset latency, improved sleep consistency and patterns, and reduced sleep anxiety following a successful cognitive restructuring

programme. Furthermore, although the insomnia and sleep problems were not completely cured due to a shortage of time, the participants had reported a reduction in the severity of insomnia from an average medium severity at baseline to very mild severity post-intervention.

Likewise, the results of the present study align with the vast literature confirming that CBT-based interventions like cognitive restructuring are quite effective in treating fatigue, including both the physical and psychological aspects of fatigue. As per the findings of Bempohl et al. (2024), CBT-based methods alleviate fatigue moderately. While the post-treatment effects were significant, follow-up assessments revealed that the advantages were partially maintained over time, while the effect sizes varied. These findings support the use of CBT-based therapies like cognitive restructuring to treat fatigue and associated psychological distress, demonstrating their potential for long-term symptom management.

Finally, the last objective of the present study, i.e., assessing whether somatic symptoms will be significant predictor of insomnia and fatigue has been found significant. The findings of the present study showed that a high level of variance in the scores of insomnia and fatigue were predicted by the scores of somatic symptoms.

These findings emphasize the relevance of cognitive restructuring approaches in controlling physical symptoms, implying that CR may be the recommended solution for patients and individuals suffering from somatic complaints and sleep-related issues.

5. Limitations

Limitations of the present study are:

1. The present study had a small total sample i.e., (N=17). This sample size was very small, which could have been greater to ensure increased generalizability.
2. Clinical interviews should have been conducted in order to achieve a more pure sample.
3. The present study was time-bound, due to which long-term follow-up of the participants was not possible.
4. Only a single technique of CBT (cognitive restructuring) was used, excluding others, which could specify the results of the study.
5. The intervention was conducted during the month of Ramzan, which could have greatly impacted the routines and well-being of the participants due to hectic schedules

6. Conclusion

The present study sought to examine the efficacy of Cognitive Restructuring (CR) in treating somatic symptoms (SSS), insomnia (RIS), and fatigue (FAS) among university students. Given the high rates of prevalence of these issues among the student population, this study sheds light on the importance of establishing the effectiveness of psychological treatment for symptom reduction. The study anticipated that students would experience a lower number and severity of symptoms of somatic complaints, insomnia, and fatigue after the successful conduction of the intervention being used in this study. The sample (N=21) of

the present study was collected from Islamia College University, Peshawar, KPK. In this study, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test was used to assess the difference between pre-intervention and post-intervention scores for Cognitive Restructuring on somatic symptoms, insomnia and fatigue.

The findings of the present study provide comprehensive results regarding the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring in reducing somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue. The results confirmed that CR is effective treatment option for somatic symptoms, insomnia, and fatigue and led to statistically significant improvements in symptom severity across all variables. This indicates that in order to treat psychosomatic symptoms, the psychological (cognitive) aspect can be targeted to get significant results. CR consistently showed superior results throughout all the statistical tests and analyses, indicating that targeting maladaptive thought patterns and cognitive distortions is very beneficial for treatment.

Specifically, the study discovered that CR significantly decreased somatic symptom complaints, which is consistent with previous studies demonstrating that CBT-based therapies can restructure stressful thoughts, reducing perceived body distress and anxiety. Similarly, CR had a significant influence on sleep quality, as it reduced insomnia severity while also improving sleep onset latency and consistency, supporting previous research that challenging negative beliefs about sleep reduces pre-sleep arousal and sleep-related anxiety. Furthermore, the CR intervention resulted in significant fatigue reductions, suggesting that altering cognitive distortions regarding exhaustion and stress will improve energy levels and coping skills.

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